

Similarity Based Retrieval in Case Based Reasoning for Analysis of Medical Images

Authors : M. Dasgupta, S. Banerjee

Abstract : Content Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) coupled with Case Based Reasoning (CBR) is a paradigm that is becoming increasingly popular in the diagnosis and therapy planning of medical ailments utilizing the digital content of medical images. This paper presents a survey of some of the promising approaches used in the detection of abnormalities in retina images as well in mammographic screening and detection of regions of interest in MRI scans of the brain. We also describe our proposed algorithm to detect hard exudates in fundus images of the retina of Diabetic Retinopathy patients.

Keywords : case based reasoning, exudates, retina image, similarity based retrieval

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